

MODEL B

STATISTICAL QUESTIONS

*Date: *Age: *Gender: *CURRENT TIME AT THE BEGINIG:

*Studies: *Profession:

() Information collected for statistical purposes.*

Current course degree:

Have you ever used Excel charts to visualize data? (Yes/No):
In the case of answering Yes, mark: (Lay/Regular/Expert)

Have you ever used data visualization tools such as Power BI or Tableau? (Yes/No):
In the case of answering Yes, mark: (Lay/Regular/Expert)

Have you ever used any programming tool to generate visualizations such as Google Charts or D3.js?
(Yes/No):
In the case of answering Yes, mark: (Lay/Regular/Expert)

You consider yourself an Expert/Non-expert user in analysis and data visualization.

EXERCISE 1

Put yourself in the shoes of a tax collector from a company in charge of collecting taxes for your province.

Your bosses ask you to **reduce tax collection time**. You have available the data shown below:

Table: Location	Table: Expedient	Table: Receipt
- Coordinates	- Id	- Code
- Organism	- Name	- Concept
- Municipality	- NIF	- Amount
- Province	- Type	- Type
- Community	- Phone	- State
		- IdExpedient
		- CodOrganism
		- YearEmission
		- MonthEmission
		- DayEmission
		- YearPayment
		- MonthPayment
		- DayPayment
		- YearLimit
		- MonthLimit
		- DayLimit

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Which visualization or visualizations of the ones shown below would you choose to achieve your goal? Choose the visualization/s and make a mockup of the visualizations defining the attributes they represent on each axis.

Column 		
Pie Chart 		
Histogram 		
Bubble Chart 		
Funnel Chart 		
Radar Chart 		

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EXERCISE 1 VISUALIZATIONS (DRAW HERE THE VISUALIZATIONS)

Example:

Axis Y: Quantity

Line: Product

Axis X: Year

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EXERCISE 2

Put yourself in the shoes of a tax collector from a company in charge of collecting taxes for your province.

Your bosses ask you to **reduce the unpaid bills**. You have available the data shown below:

<p>Table: Location</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinates - Organism - Municipality - Province - Community 	<p>Table: Expedient</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Id - Name - NIF - Type - Phone 	<p>Table: Receipt</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Code - Concept - Amount - Type - State - IdExpedient - CodOrganism - YearEmission - MonthEmission - DayEmission - YearPayment - MonthPayment - DayPayment - YearLimit - MonthLimit - DayLimit
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In this case, instead of directly selecting the visualization, we are going to reflect on how to carry out the analysis to achieve the goal and on the goals that each visualization has to meet and thus be able to know the most appropriate type of visualization for each case.

For this reason, a goal tree like the one shown below will be made.

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Goal tree

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* Follow the diagram to select the visualization objective/s that each visualization must meet.

After completing the goal tree, fill in the gray gaps in the summary table below.

Summary Table

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Information Goals

	<i>Analyze the products with the highest profit</i>					
User (Lay/Tech)	<i>Lay</i>					
Visualization/s Goals	<i>Comparison y Order</i>					
Interaction/s	<i>Overview</i>					
Dimensionality	<i>2-dimensional</i>					
Cardinality	<i>Low</i>					
Independent Type	<i>Nominal</i>					
Dependent Type	<i>Ratio</i>					
VISUALIZATION TYPE	<i>COLUMN GRAPH</i>					

Use the **DATA CLASSIFICATION TABLE (Annex 1)** to define the remaining gaps in your table (**Dimensionality, Cardinality, Independent Type, Dependent Type ***)

* *The dependent/independent type indicates whether one variable depends on another. Ex. The variables Profit and Product, the variable Product is independent and Profit is dependent, since it varies according to the product.*

Use the **SUITABILITY TABLES (Annex 2)** to choose the most suitable type of visualization for each information goal. Write the selected visualization type in the summary table.

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EXERCISE 2 VISUALIZATIONS (DRAW HERE THE VISUALIZATIONS)

Use the most suitable visualization type according to the **SUITABILITY TABLES**.

Example:

Axis Y: Quantity

Line: Product

Axis X: Year

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EVALUATION

Reduce tax collection time (Exercise 1)

These are the needs that you will find. Can you answer them with the visualization/s that you have created? Write "YES" if you have been able to answer them or "NO" if you have not been able to answer them.

	YES/NO
Identify the amount of bills paid on and after the deadline	
Identify the types of bills that are mostly paid after the deadline	
Indicate in which areas there are payment delays	
Identify the most delayed tax records	

Reduce the unpaid bills (Exercise 2)

These are the needs that you will find. Can you answer them with the visualization/s that you have created? Write "YES" if you have been able to answer them or "NO" if you have not been able to answer them.

	YES/NO
Identify the areas with most unpaid bills	
Identify the types of taxes with most unpaid bills	
Identify the tax records with most unpaid bills	
Analyze the evolution over time of unpaid bills	

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For each question below, select from 1 to 4 the option that you think is most appropriate

	1	2	3	4
Are the visualizations useful? Is the information well represented? Are the visualizations suitable for the information? (EXERCISE 1)	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Totally agree
Are the visualizations useful? Is the information well represented? Are the visualizations suitable for the information? (EXERCISE 2)	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Totally agree
Did you perceive any improvement in Ex. 2 over Ex. 1?	No improvement	Little improvement	Reasonable improvement	Remarkable improvement

COMMENTS:

CURRENT TIME AT THE END:

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ANNEX 1 - DATA CLASSIFICATION TABLE

Location

	Cardinality	Type
- Coordinates	High	Interval
- Organism	High	Nominal
- Municipality	High	Nominal
- Province	Low	Nominal
- Community	Low	Nominal

Expedient

	Cardinality	Type
- Id	High	Ratio
- Name	High	Nominal
- NIF	High	Interval
- Type	Low	Nominal
- Phone	High	Interval

Receipt

	Cardinality	Type
- Code	High	Nominal
- Concept	High	Nominal
- Amount	High	Ratio
- Type	Low	Nominal
- State	Low	Ordinal
- IdExpedient	High	Interval
- CodOrganism	High	Interval
- YearEmission	Low	Interval
- MonthEmission	Low	Interval
- DayEmission	Low	Interval
- YearPayment	Low	Interval
- MonthPayment	Low	Interval
- DayPayment	Low	Interval
- YearLimit	Low	Interval
- MonthLimit	Low	Interval
- DayLimit	Low	Interval

Dimensionality: → number of columns to visualize

- **1-dimensional:** A single value
- **2-dimensional:** Two variables
- **n-dimensional:** More than two variables
- **Tree:** A collection of items, each having a link to one parent item
- **Graph:** A collection of items, each linked to an arbitrary number of other items

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ANNEX 2 - SUITABILITY TABLES

fit > acceptable > discouraged > unfit

	A) Stacked column graph	B) Single line graph	C) Marked line graph	D) Pie chart	E) Bubble graph
USER					
Lay	fit	fit	fit	fit	acceptable
Tech	fit	fit	fit	acceptable	fit
VISUALIZATION GOAL					
Composition	fit	unfit	unfit	fit	discouraged
Order	unfit	discouraged	unfit	unfit	unfit
Relationship	discouraged	unfit	unfit	unfit	fit
Comparison	fit	unfit	unfit	unfit	fit
Cluster	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit	acceptable
Distribution	acceptable	acceptable	acceptable	unfit	fit
Trend	discouraged	fit	fit	unfit	acceptable
Geospatial	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit	discouraged
INTERACTION					
Overview	acceptable	fit	fit	fit	fit
Zoom	acceptable	acceptable	acceptable	unfit	acceptable
Filter	discouraged	discouraged	discouraged	acceptable	discouraged
Details-on-demand	discouraged	acceptable	fit	acceptable	acceptable
DIMENSIONALITY					
1-dimensional	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit
2- dimensional	discouraged	fit	fit	fit	unfit
n- dimensional	fit	unfit	unfit	unfit	fit
Tree	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit
Graph	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit
CARDINALITY					
Low	fit	acceptable	fit	fit	acceptable
High	discouraged	fit	discouraged	discouraged	discouraged
INDEPENDENT TYPE					
Nominal	fit	unfit	unfit	fit	unfit
Ordinal	fit	discouraged	discouraged	acceptable	discouraged
Interval	discouraged	fit	fit	discouraged	fit
Ratio	discouraged	fit	fit	discouraged	fit
DEPENDENT TYPE					
Nominal	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit	fit
Ordinal	discouraged	unfit	unfit	unfit	fit
Interval	fit	fit	fit	discouraged	acceptable
Ratio	fit	fit	fit	fit	fit

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	F) Grouped column graph	G) Map	H) Dendrogram	I) Treemap	J) Column graph	K) Multi-line graph
USER						
Lay	fit	acceptable	acceptable	discouraged	fit	fit
Tech	fit	fit	fit	fit	fit	fit
VISUALIZATION GOAL						
Composition	acceptable	unfit	acceptable	acceptable	unfit	unfit
Order	acceptable	unfit	discouraged	unfit	fit	unfit
Relationship	discouraged	unfit	acceptable	fit	unfit	discouraged
Comparison	fit	acceptable	discouraged	acceptable	fit	acceptable
Cluster	acceptable	acceptable	fit	fit	unfit	unfit
Distribution	acceptable	fit	discouraged	discouraged	acceptable	acceptable
Trend	fit	unfit	unfit	unfit	fit	fit
Geospatial	unfit	fit	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit
INTERACTION						
Overview	fit	fit	fit	fit	fit	fit
Zoom	unfit	fit	fit	acceptable	acceptable	acceptable
Filter	acceptable	acceptable	acceptable	acceptable	acceptable	acceptable
Details-on-demand	acceptable	acceptable	acceptable	acceptable	acceptable	acceptable
DIMENSIONALITY						
1-dimensional	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit
2- dimensional	unfit	fit	unfit	unfit	fit	unfit
n- dimensional	fit	fit	unfit	acceptable	unfit	fit
Tree	unfit	unfit	fit	fit	unfit	unfit
Graph	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit	unfit
CARDINALITY						
Low	fit	acceptable	fit	fit	fit	fit
High	discouraged	fit	acceptable	acceptable	discouraged	acceptable
INDEPENDENT TYPE						
Nominal	fit	acceptable	fit	fit	fit	fit
Ordinal	fit	acceptable	discouraged	discouraged	fit	fit
Interval	acceptable	fit	discouraged	discouraged	acceptable	fit
Ratio	acceptable	fit	unfit	unfit	acceptable	fit
DEPENDENT TYPE						
Nominal	unfit	unfit	unfit	fit	unfit	unfit
Ordinal	unfit	discouraged	unfit	discouraged	unfit	unfit
Interval	discouraged	fit	acceptable	discouraged	discouraged	fit
Ratio	fit	fit	fit	fit	fit	fit

